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Sustainable Management of soil Organic Matter to Mitigate Trade-offs between C sequestration and nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses

Deliverable 6.7

Guidelines on soil management options to mitigate trade-off between C seq and GHG emissions, per pedo-climatic area, at territorial scale

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ABSTRACT

Deliverable 6.7 is planned within the SOMMIT Sub-task “WP6-T2-ST3 Open dialog on soil management strategies” which has the ambition to start up a circular process of feedback between researchers and stakeholders of the Stakeholders’ Platforms (SPs) on the project outputs. In this context the guidelines represent the final synthesis of the discussion held around the Soil Management Strategies (SMSs) under study in the different Long-Term Experiments (LTEs) of the living labs (LLs) participating in the task activities. The practices covered in this document are those under study in the LTEs representing the biophysical components of the LLs activated within the project, with a view to working on a territorial scale. As primary source of information for the definition of the guidelines, this document considers both the opinions of the researchers built during the years of the LTE monitoring and those of the SPs gathered in the various phases of involvement envisaged in the project. Opinions from researchers and from stakeholders are considered with same weights, reflecting the inclusive and participatory process carried on within the task 6.2.

The guidelines on virtuous SMSs are designed to highlight the **opportunities and risks** of their application in a schematic way and usable by a wide audience, with a focus on possible solutions to overcome the associated risks. They may be supporting material for the continuation of the extra-project debate on SMSs.

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

LL: Living Lab

LTE: Long term experiment

SMSs: Soil Management Strategies

SP: Stakeholders' platform

1. Introduction & Context

Soil holds an important role in mitigating climate change. Proper soil use and management can potentially enhance carbon sequestration while reducing net GHG emissions. Virtuous soil management strategies in agriculture would be a valuable tool for climate change adaptation and a pathway for safeguarding key ecosystem services and biodiversity. The SOMMIT project has evaluated trade-offs and synergies between soil C sequestration, nitrous oxide, methane and nitrate losses as affected by SMSs aimed at increasing soil C storage. Within SOMMIT, task 6.2 has developed a path of stakeholders' involvement around the debate on effective SMSs, especially on those tested in the LTEs monitored during the project. The effective involvement of stakeholders, mainly farmers, represents a powerful tool to validate SMSs at territorial scale. By enabling farmers to design the research agenda around the LTE practices, as well as involve them in a critical debate on tested SMSs, effective solutions could be found to overcome the barriers on their operative application.

2. Objectives of the guidelines and target

The main aim of the guidelines is to contribute to the awareness of stakeholders regarding risks/benefits associated to sustainable soil management, with reference to the maintenance of the soil organic matter and the mitigation of GHG emissions, through a series of practical and direct information, as well as insights into possible solutions to overcome the risks, and may be supporting material for the continuation of the extra-project debate.

The guidelines, while maintaining a strictly operational format, are not conceived as a manual nor a scientific document, referring to specific bibliographic references for more technical and theoretical aspects. Guidelines are instead conceived as a tool useful to activate a comparison, rendered in summary form, between knowledge and experience belonging to different professional fields (i.e. the SOMMIT stakeholders' platform), to promote and disseminate a shared and sustainable approach to the design and management of soil in agroecosystems.

3. The Guidelines on Soil Management Strategies

The SMS under consideration for the guidelines are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. SMSs studied in the LTEs of the sites

LTE	AGROECOSYSTEM	PRACTICE	SCALING
IT-MAIOR	Organic fruit orchard	AGROFORESTRY	Horticultural/arable systems
IT-MAIOR	Organic fruit orchard	MINIMUM/REDUCED TILLAGE	Horticultural/arable systems
IT-MAIOR	Organic fruit orchard	COMPOST USE	Horticultural/arable systems
IT-MAIOR	Organic fruit orchard	COVER CROPS	Horticultural/arable systems
AT-AGES	Arable system	MINIMUM/REDUCED TILLAGE	Horticultural
SI-ULBF	Arable system	MINIMUM/REDUCED TILLAGE	Horticultural
SI-ULBF	Arable system	COMPOST USE	Horticultural
SI-ULBF	Arable system	COVER CROPS	Horticultural

3.1 COVER CROPS

3.1.1 Introduction

The introduction of crops not directly devoted to production but to provide ecosystem services (such as supply organic matter to soil, catch nutrients reducing potential leaching, attraction of beneficial insects, etc...) represents an important practice for the sustainable management of the agroecosystem in the inter-rows of fruit orchards, but also in the rotation of vegetable and arable systems.

The choice of cover crop species or mixtures is decisive for the farm objectives and for targeting the provision of specific services. The main goals can be agronomic (soil conservation and improvement of soil fertility, control of weeds and pathogens and parasites) or environmental (reduction of energy consumption from non-renewable sources, reduction of nitrate leaching, reduction of pesticide use). These objectives are closely related to the pedoclimatic characteristics of the farm (soil type, nutrient deficiencies, presence of pests, climate), which may need for these services at different levels.

3.1.2 Operational aspects

Species choice

The cover crop can be chosen depending on the soil coverage period of interest, the farm irrigation availability as well as the expected services, so they can be autumn-winter or spring-summer species. The cover crop species typically introduced belong to three main families: Brassicaceae, Fabaceae, and Poaceae. Each of them held peculiar characteristics that should be carefully considered when selecting the most suitable cover crop species or mixture to achieve specific goals.

Brassicaceae: characterised by a rapid initial development, high aerial biomass and a root system that develops depending on the species. They are particularly useful for their biocidal and nematocidal effect due to the release of glucosinolates.

Fabaceae: particularly used for enriching the soil in N, due to their ability to create a symbiosis with nitrogen-fixing bacteria able to convert atmospheric nitrogen into organic nitrogen. Leguminosae represent an important opportunity to reduce external nitrogen inputs to the system.

Poaceae: widely used as cover crops because of the high biomass development which implies an important input of organic matter to soil and competition with weeds. Also used as catch crops due to the fibrous root system which allows the retention of nutrients and limitation of leaching.

Sowing

In general, cover crops provide the expected results (e.g. weed control, increased soil organic matter content, nitrogen fixation) if they produce abundant aerial and root biomass. However, cover crops are often cultivated at times of the year unsuitable for cash crops, when the climate is unfavourable and the growing season relatively short. For example, for autumn-winter cover crops, radiation and temperature gradually decrease during the autumn to become very limiting in the winter. Therefore, cover crop management must maximise the efficient use of the available resources (solar radiation, temperature, water and nutrients). Good establishment and initial rapid growth are essential. These can be achieved by sowing at the most appropriate time in relation to the species and environment, and with techniques capable of ensuring rapid and homogeneous emergence of the crop.

Termination

Mechanical termination may involve only the aerial part of the cover crop (chopping, mowing and rolling) or the soil and the roots (ploughing, discing, scaling); the first are chosen for broadcast seeding or when there is the need to facilitating the subsequent incorporation of the cover crop into the soil.

3.1.3 Opportunities

Cover crops can bring several agronomic and environmental benefits:

Improvement of soil physical and biological quality

Soil coverage reduces soil erosion and soil compaction by improving soil structure. The presence of cover crop roots promotes the growth of soil aggregates and increases the activity of microorganisms, which in turn improves the stability of the structure. The root system of cover crops also acts on the permeability of the soil by increasing the water infiltration.

Reduction of GHG emissions and improvement of C storing

Cover crops can significantly reduce GHG emissions by sequestering carbon in the soil and decreasing the need for external fertilizers. Cover crops' root systems enhance soil structure and organic matter, promoting carbon storage. After the termination, the cover crop biomass becomes a food substrate for soil micro-organisms from whose activity humic substances are derived. Additionally, by covering the soil, they reduce nitrous oxide emissions from soil microbial activity.

Increase in nitrogen and nutrients

During their growth, cover crops absorb nitrogen and other important nutrients, saving them from leaching and returning to the soil in organic form. Leguminous cover crops also fix atmospheric nitrogen through symbiosis with nitrogen-fixing bacteria and therefore increase soil N content.

Weed control

Weed growth is limited due to competition for space, water and nutrients with the cover crop, and the allelopathic action of certain species. Depending on the termination strategy adopted, the presence of a mulch (mowing, rolling) or the release of allelopathic compounds (e.g. ploughing) can reduce seedling emergence also after the cover crop cycle.

Increase of agroecosystem biodiversity and promotion of functional biodiversity

Cover crops (but also flower strips and green infrastructure in general) are some of the agroecological practices most frequently used to enhance habitats of pollinating insects and natural enemies. Green infrastructures are known to provide the missing habitat requirements for natural enemies (food resources, shelters, refuges, etc.), allowing them to overcome the disturbances derived from agricultural practices.

The combination of these agronomic-environmental benefits results in economic advantages often difficult to quantify, especially in the short term. In the medium / long term, the improvement in soil structure and its content of nutrients and organic substance can allow a reduction in the need for tillage and less fertiliser use.

3.1.4 Risks and possible solutions

Costs for cover crops management without a corresponding direct income

This is a common perception on the practice implementation, the introduction of cover crops requires investments in the seeds, soil preparation and sowing, and final termination, in the short-term this is not compensated by a return in saleable product. However, a more long-term and holistic vision should consider the advantages obtained in terms of soil quality, declined also in the availability of nutrients, which reduces the need to purchase external inputs. The availability of seeds of different cover crop species at the local scale could be crucial to overcome the limit in their adoption. In a nutshell, seed companies able to produce seed of species to satisfy the needs of local farmers should be supported, promoting the setup of value-added supply chain of these materials.

Potential productivity reduction due to competition or asynchrony in nutrient release after termination

To expand the species options available to farmers is a keystone in promoting cover crops adoption. Besides, farmers should be supported in identifying both the correct species and termination strategies (i.e. time and method of termination) to limit the risks and tackle the opportunities offered by cover crop introduction.

Difficulties in cover crops managements

One of the main difficult is to find the right window of cultivation in the rotation respect to the principal crop and the right time to terminate them.

Collaboration between farmers and research in multi-actor experiences could magnify the local knowledge on both the choice of the correct species/mix of species and the management strategies. Moreover, participatory environments, as the living labs, could promote the exchange of experiences and knowledge among practitioners, in a peer-to-peer context as well as testing the options in real life settings (i.e., the real farms).

3.2 MINIMUM/REDUCED TILLAGE

3.2.1 Introduction

The adoption of minimum or reduced tillage practices, which involves limiting soil disturbance to essential operations only, represents a significant tool in sustainable agriculture. This method helps to maintain soil structure, reduce erosion, conserve moisture, and to enhance soil organic matter. Implementing reduced tillage can lead to improved soil health and increased biodiversity, as it creates a more stable environment for soil microorganisms and beneficial insects.

Choosing the appropriate tillage method is crucial for achieving specific agronomic and environmental goals. These goals may include improving soil fertility, reducing weed pressure, and minimizing the reliance on chemical inputs. Furthermore, reduced tillage contributes to the reduction of GHG emissions and energy consumption by decreasing the need for mechanical operations (Six et al., 2004). It also promotes carbon sequestration in the soil, enhancing carbon storage and mitigating climate change impacts. The effectiveness of these practices is highly dependent on the farm's pedoclimatic conditions, including soil type, moisture levels, and climate. Tailoring the tillage approach to these conditions is essential for maximizing the benefits and ensuring long-term sustainability.

3.2.2 Operational aspects

Equipment and Machinery

The implementation of minimum tillage requires specialized equipment designed to disturb the soil as little as possible, such as chisel plows, disc harrows, and strip-till machines. These tools till only narrow strips where seeds are to be planted, leaving the rest of the field undisturbed. Choosing the right equipment is crucial for the success of minimum tillage and depends on soil type, crop requirements, and field conditions.

Timing and Soil Conditions

Proper timing of tillage operations is essential to minimize soil compaction and ensure optimal seedbed conditions. Tillage should be performed when the soil is neither too wet nor too dry to avoid damage to soil structure. Monitoring soil moisture levels and weather forecasts helps in planning the best times for tillage operations.

Residue Management

Managing crop residues is a key component of minimum tillage systems. Residues left on the soil surface protect against erosion, retain soil moisture, and contribute to organic matter. Proper distribution of residues during harvest and after tillage ensures uniform coverage, which helps to suppress weeds and provides a microclimate favourable to beneficial soil organisms. Residue management practices must be tailored to the specific crop and local conditions to maximize benefits.

Weed Management

Weed management is a critical challenge in minimum tillage systems due to the reduced soil disturbance. Widening crop rotation, also integrating cover crops, and mechanical termination methods such as mulching and rolling (e.g. conservative agriculture with direct sowing), can help to manage weed pressure. Cover crops play indeed a significant role, competing with weeds for resources and providing a physical barrier. Herbicide use in non-organic systems should be minimized to reduce environmental impact.

Soil Fertility and Amendments

Maintaining soil fertility is crucial in minimum tillage systems as reduced soil disturbance can affect nutrient distribution and availability. Soil testing is essential to monitor nutrient levels and identify deficiencies. Organic amendments, such as compost and manure, can improve soil structure and fertility. Fertilizers should be applied to maximize uptake by crops and minimize losses to the environment.

Monitoring and Adaptation

Regular monitoring of soil health and crop performance is necessary to adapt management practices and ensure the success of minimum tillage. This includes tracking soil moisture, organic matter levels, and crop yields. Farmers should be prepared to adjust their practices based on observed outcomes and changing conditions. Continuous learning and adaptation are key to optimizing the benefits of minimum tillage over time.

3.2.3 Opportunities

Soil Health Improvement

Adopting minimum tillage practices significantly enhances soil health by preserving soil structure, reducing compaction, and increasing organic matter content. These improvements facilitate better water infiltration and retention, crucial for mitigating drought impacts and improving crop resilience.

Carbon Sequestration and Climate Change Mitigation

Minimum tillage contributes to carbon sequestration by minimizing soil disturbance, thus enhancing carbon storage in the soil and reducing atmospheric carbon dioxide levels. This practice also decreases fuel consumption and GHG emissions, aligning with sustainable farming goals.

Cost Savings and Efficiency

Implementing minimum tillage results in significant cost savings due to reduced fuel and labour requirements for tillage operations. Lower machinery wear and tear further decreases maintenance costs, improving overall farm's profitability. This efficiency allows farmers to allocate resources more effectively.

Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services

Minimum tillage supports greater biodiversity both above and below ground. Preserving soil structure and surface residues create habitats for beneficial soil organisms and insects, contributing to nutrient cycling, pest control, and pollination. Enhanced biodiversity strengthens agroecosystem resilience and reduces dependency on chemical inputs.

Adaptability to Different Cropping Systems

The versatility of minimum tillage makes it suitable for various cropping systems, including row crops, orchards, and vegetables. It can be integrated with other sustainable practices like crop rotation and cover cropping to optimize benefits. Tailoring practices to specific crops and local conditions enhances productivity and sustainability.

Water Conservation

Improved soil structure and organic matter content through minimum tillage enhance water infiltration and retention. This reduces irrigation needs and improves water use efficiency, critical in regions prone to water scarcity. Enhanced moisture retention supports consistent crop growth and yields.

Reduction in Soil Erosion

By maintaining crop residues on the soil surface, minimum tillage acts as a barrier against erosion caused by wind and water. This practice preserves soil fertility and productivity, particularly on sloping lands and in regions with heavy rainfall.

3.2.4 Risks and possible solutions

Soil Compaction

While minimum tillage practices aim to reduce soil disturbance, there is a risk of soil compaction, especially in heavier soils or under certain weather conditions. Compacted soils can hinder root penetration, reduce water infiltration, and limit nutrient uptake by plants, ultimately impacting crop productivity. To mitigate soil compaction, farmers can adopt practices such as controlled traffic farming, where machinery operates on controlled paths to minimize soil disturbance. Improving soil structure through cover crops and incorporating organic matter can also enhance soil resilience against compaction.

Challenges in Crop Rotation and Cultivation

Minimum tillage can pose challenges in managing crop rotation and cultivation. Reduced soil disturbance may hinder to incorporate crop residues effectively or prepare seedbeds for different crops. This can affect seed germination, crop establishment, and overall yield potential, requiring careful planning and management adjustments. Farmers can address these challenges by diversifying crop rotations and integrating cover crops that facilitate residue breakdown and nutrient cycling. Adjusting planting techniques and using specialized equipment designed for minimum tillage can also optimize crop establishment and yield potential.

Potential Yield Reduction

Adopting minimum tillage practices may initially lead to a reduction in yields, especially if not managed correctly or under adverse conditions. The presence of crop residues on the soil surface can create microclimatic conditions that may delay soil warming in spring, affecting early crop growth stages. However, with proper adaptation and management, the long-term benefits of improved soil health and resource efficiency can often outweigh the initial yield challenges. To mitigate potential yield reductions, farmers can implement strategies such as selecting appropriate cover crop species that decompose quickly, ensuring timely planting and termination of cover crops, and adjusting fertilizer and irrigation practices to compensate for nutrient availability in minimally disturbed soils.

Transition Challenges

Transitioning from conventional tillage to minimum tillage requires a shift in farming practices and mindset. Farmers may face challenges in adapting equipment, timing operations, and managing weeds and pests under reduced soil disturbance conditions. However, experience and learning from successful transitions can provide confidence in overcoming these challenges and optimizing the benefits of minimum tillage over time. Farmers can seek support from agricultural extension services and peer networks to learn best practices for minimum tillage adoption. Gradual implementation and phased transition plans can help manage risks and build confidence in the new farming system. Continuous monitoring and adaptive management are crucial for fine-tuning practices to local conditions and maximizing long-term sustainability.

3.3 COMPOST USE

3.3.1 Introduction

The incorporation of compost into agricultural systems serves as a pivotal strategy to enhance soil health and promote sustainability. Compost, derived from organic materials such as food waste and agricultural residues, enriches soil fertility and structure, fostering improved water retention and nutrient availability. Its utilization transcends mere nutrient supplementation; compost plays a critical role in mitigating soil erosion, enhancing microbial activity, and bolstering carbon sequestration efforts. By integrating compost into farming operations, farmers can effectively reduce dependency on synthetic fertilizers and pesticides, thereby minimizing environmental impacts and contributing to resilient agroecosystems. The selection of compost types and application methods is paramount, tailored to specific farm needs and environmental conditions to optimize its benefits. As agriculture evolves towards more sustainable paradigms, the strategic incorporation of compost stands as a cornerstone in achieving agricultural resilience and environmental stewardship.

3.3.2 Operational aspects

Choice of type

The choice of compost type and application method is crucial for achieving specific farm objectives and environmental benefits. Compost can vary widely in composition and nutrient availability, depending on the feedstocks used and the composting process employed. Generally, compost is categorized as either green (high in nitrogen) or brown (high in carbon), and the ratio of these components affects its nutrient content and decomposition rate.

Application

Compost can be applied to fields through various methods, including surface application, incorporation into the soil, or as a mulch. The method chosen depends on factors such as crop type, soil characteristics, and desired nutrient release timing. Surface application is effective for improving soil structure and moisture retention, while incorporation ensures better nutrient distribution and reduces nitrogen loss through volatilization.

Timing

The timing of compost application is critical to maximize its benefits and minimize environmental impacts. Applying compost during periods of active plant growth enhances nutrient uptake and crop productivity while reducing nutrient leaching. However, applications should be timed to avoid nutrient leaching during heavy rainfall or excessive irrigation.

Monitoring and Adjustments

Regular monitoring of soil nutrient levels and crop performance helps farmers adjust compost application rates and timing. Soil testing provides valuable insights into nutrient availability and ensures that compost application meets crop nutrient requirements without exceeding environmental thresholds.

3.3.3 Opportunities

The utilization of compost in agriculture offers opportunities that toward economic, environmental, and agronomic benefits. Direct experiences with compost have underscored its efficacy as a cost-effective material, readily produced on-farm, thereby promoting greater resource circularity and sustainability. Compost enhances soil's capacity for long-term moisture retention and organic fertility, thereby bolstering overall system productivity and resilience.

Enhanced Soil Health and Nutrient Cycling

Compost application enriches soil with essential nutrients in a slow-release form, promoting balanced nutrient availability throughout the crop growth cycle. This fosters improved soil structure and microbial activity, enhancing nutrient uptake efficiency and reducing dependence on synthetic fertilizers.

Climate Mitigation and Carbon Sequestration

An often-overlooked benefit of compost is its role in carbon sequestration, contributing to mitigating climate change impacts by storing atmospheric carbon dioxide in soils. This not only stabilizes soil organic carbon levels but also improves soil structure and stability, mitigating erosion and enhancing water infiltration rates.

Economic Efficiency and Resource Conservation

By substituting synthetic inputs with compost, farmers can reduce operational costs while maintaining or even improving crop yields and quality. Compost's role in enhancing soil fertility and water-holding capacity translates into improved resilience against drought and other environmental stresses, thereby safeguarding farm productivity and profitability.

Integration with Sustainable Agriculture Practices

Compost fits perfectly with sustainable agriculture principles, enhancing ecosystem health and biodiversity by boosting soil biological activity. Its use aids natural mechanisms for pest and disease

control, lessening the need for chemical treatments and fostering ecological balance in farming systems.

3.3.4 Risks and possible solutions

While compost offers substantial benefits to agriculture, there are inherent risks that must be addressed to ensure its effective and safe use. Perceived risks often revolve around the variability in nutrient release and uncertainties regarding compost composition and quality, particularly concerning the potential accumulation of pollutants, especially in compost derived from municipal solid wastes. Direct farmers' experiences highlight concerns about the presence of weed seeds in on-farm compost, which can pose challenges to crop management and yield.

Nutrient Release Variability

One of the primary concerns associated with compost use is the unpredictability of nutrient release rates. Variations in compost composition and maturity can affect the timing and availability of nutrients to crops, potentially leading to suboptimal nutrient management and crop performance. To mitigate this risk, farmers might conduct soil testing and adopt nutrient management plans tailored to the specific nutrient release patterns of compost used.

Composition and Quality Assurance

Uncertainties regarding compost composition and quality pose risks related to potential contaminants, such as heavy metals and pathogens, especially in compost sourced from mixed municipal solid wastes. Quality assurance measures, including regular testing and certification programs, are essential to ensure that compost meets safety standards and regulatory requirements. Farmers are encouraged to source compost from reputable suppliers or produce it on-farm using controlled feedstocks and composting techniques. In the case of on-farm compost, special attention should be paid in the process, avoiding risk of residues from fermentation and presence of weed seeds in the material.

Pollutants, Particularly Plastics

Growing concerns over pollutants, particularly microplastics, in compost have prompted farmers to seek certified products bearing a CE mark or equivalent assurance of quality and safety. While certified compost products are not yet widely available, efforts are underway to establish standards and certifications that address concerns about contaminants and ensure product integrity.

To address the risks associated with compost use, integrated pest management strategies can help mitigate weed seed contamination in on-farm compost. Mechanical screening and heat treatment techniques can effectively reduce weed seed viability before compost application. Additionally, implementing best management practices for compost handling and application, such as proper storage and application timing, can minimize potential risks and optimize compost benefits in agricultural systems.

3.4 AGROFORESTRY

3.4.1 Introduction

Agroforestry represents a transformative approach to enhancing the sustainability and resilience of agricultural systems by integrating trees, crops, and eventually livestock (agro-zoo-forestry) to create mutually beneficial interactions. This multifaceted practice aims to strengthen agricultural productivity while fostering environmental health and economic viability. In agroforestry systems, the synergies between trees, crops, (and animals) can offer substantial benefits. These include improved biodiversity, reduced soil erosion, and enhanced soil fertility through nutrient cycling and organic matter enrichment. Moreover, trees can act as windbreaks, offer shade, and contribute to carbon sequestration, thus playing a pivotal role in climate change mitigation. However, adopting agroforestry requires meticulous planning and a thorough knowhow for understanding the biological interactions among the components. It is essential to consider local ecological conditions, soil characteristics, and

crop preferences to optimize the benefits. Effective implementation also involves integrating traditional knowledge with scientific research to tailor practices that suit specific local needs and environmental conditions.

3.4.2 Operational aspects

Agroforestry implementation requires a holistic, evidence-based approach tailored to specific local conditions and agronomic needs. By adopting appropriate design and management practices, farmers can fully exploit the potential of agroforestry to promote soil health, improve productivity, and mitigate environmental impacts. Therefore, implementing agroforestry requires a series of practical and operational considerations to maximize agronomic and environmental benefits within fruit, arable, and horticultural systems.

Agroforestry System Design

Considering soil characteristics, pedoclimatic conditions, and local crop preferences is pivotal when designing an agroforestry system. In fruit systems, selecting herbaceous or arable crops that complement the main fruit trees is essential. These crops should contribute to nutrient cycling and support soil health without competing for resources, according to the mechanism of complementation and niche differentiation. In herbaceous systems, optimizing the interaction between trees and crops can improve resource utilization and enhance crop yields. Trees can provide beneficial partial shading, wind protection and habitat for beneficial organisms to the crops thereby promoting sustainability and productivity within the system.

Species and Variety Selection

The selection of tree species and crop varieties is critical for the success of agroforestry. Tree species should be chosen based on their compatibility with local conditions, their ability to provide ecosystem services such as nitrogen fixation or timber production, and their resistance to diseases and pests. Crop varieties should complement the tree species, ensuring harmonious coexistence and maximizing mutual benefits.

Management and Maintenance

Effective management of agroforestry systems is essential to optimize agricultural production and minimize environmental impacts. This includes practices such as pruning trees to manage shading and promote production, managing weeds to ensure crop competitiveness, and balanced irrigation and fertilization to support optimal growth.

Continuous Monitoring and Evaluation

Regular monitoring of the agroforestry system's performance is crucial to assess the effectiveness of adopted practices and make necessary adjustments. This can include measuring crop and tree growth, monitoring soil quality, and evaluating local biodiversity. The information collected allows farmers to adapt their management strategies to maximize benefits and address emerging challenges.

3.4.3 Opportunities

Agroforestry represents a significant opportunity to enhance the sustainability and resilience of agricultural systems, offering a range of benefits including greenhouse gas emission reduction and carbon sequestration, alongside diversifying agricultural income and improving soil quality.

Reduction of Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Carbon Sequestration

Implementing agroforestry systems facilitates the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions by capturing and sequestering atmospheric carbon in soil and tree biomass. This process contributes to mitigating climate change while enhancing soil fertility and structural stability, reducing erosion and increasing water retention capacity.

Income Diversification and Soil System Improvement

Agroforestry provides a unique opportunity to diversify agricultural income by integrating the production of crops with the cultivation of high-value timber, fruit trees, or other tree species. This

diversification reduces financial risks for farmers and promotes economic resilience in agricultural systems.

Resource use improvement

The interaction between trees and crops in agroforestry systems improves resource use complementarity, optimizing nutrient absorption efficiency and water use. This complementarity enhances soil quality through nutrient cycling and reduced plant competition, supporting increased productivity and system stability.

Biodiversity Benefits and Multifunctionality

Direct farmers' experiences demonstrate that agroforestry promotes greater biodiversity in agricultural systems, both in terms of vegetation and soil life, enhancing agroecosystem multifunctionality. This translates into ecological benefits such as conservation of native flora and fauna, protection of beneficial insect habitats, and promotion of ecosystem services such as water cycle regulation and microclimate stabilization.

3.4.4 Risks and possible solutions

Implementation of agroforestry entails risks and challenges that must be addressed to maximize environmental and agronomic benefits, including managing practical complexity and mitigating productivity losses.

Managing Complexity

Agroforestry involves the integrated management of trees and crops (and animals), which can be complex and require specific skills. The need to optimize mechanization poses a significant challenge, as traditional agricultural equipment may not be suitable for simultaneous management of trees and crops in agroforestry systems. Innovative solutions, such as developing specialized equipment and advanced management techniques, are crucial to enhance operational efficiency and reduce management costs. At the same time, the establishment of a shared machinery pool among farmers can allow farmers to collectively invest in and utilize specialized equipment tailored for agroforestry tasks, thereby optimizing operational efficiency, reducing costs, and overcoming the barrier of machinery availability. Finally, the integration of herbaceous and perennial crops could open to difficulties in positioning the products in the market, suggesting the need to promote with consumers and communities the role of such systems in terms of sustainability, promoting their added value.

Risk of Productivity Loss

Integrating trees into agricultural systems can pose a risk of productivity loss in main crops, especially during the initial phases of transitioning to agroforestry systems. Competition for light, water, and nutrients can negatively influence crop growth and yield if not managed properly. Effective strategies to mitigate this risk include careful selection of tree species and crop varieties, precise planning of agroforestry system layout to optimize use of available resources, and adoption of balanced management techniques that promote complementarity between trees and crops.

Greenhouse Gas Emissions and Carbon Sequestration

Despite clear benefits, reducing GHG emissions and carbon sequestration through agroforestry systems can be influenced by soil management and agricultural practices. Soil management strategy and tree species selection influence the amount of carbon sequestered in soil and tree biomass. Sustainable management practices, such as reduced tillage and integrated weed management, can improve the effectiveness of carbon sequestration and contribute to climate change mitigation.

4 Conclusions

These guidelines have been built upon the knowledge of researchers and stakeholders (especially farmers) of the SP of the SOMMIT project regarding the opportunities and risks associated with implementing agricultural practices within the context of sustainable soil management. They aim at serving as a resource, fostering ongoing dialogue and collaboration

between operational and research compartments in agriculture, to overcome barriers and implement effective soil management practices at both local and territorial scales.

The integration of stakeholders' perspectives in public engagement initiatives developed during the project supported in evidencing weaknesses and strengths of the different soil management strategies.

It is important to remark that the involvement of stakeholders represents an opportunity for the implementation of management strategies, provided that the strengths and limitations are assessed and evaluated in the specific context of application and remembering that there exist, at a methodological level, appropriate and applicable recipes for each situation.

The wish is that the integration of stakeholder perspectives can be instrumental in validating soil management strategies tested in Long Term Experiments (LTEs) under the SOMMIT project. Furthermore, this kind of guidelines may be useful instruments in the hands of researchers and practitioners when choosing virtuous SMSs taking into consideration the evolution of society's demands, a crucial aspect during periods of rapid and important change, such the ones we are facing today.

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